

Falling ball in a viscous liquid(gas) with numerical examples

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Let us view a falling ball in a viscous liquid (gas). First, one differential equation of the falling ball in a viscous liquid (gas) is developed. Then, a solution of this differential equation is obtained through the separation of variables. The solution is the velocity function. With integration, the depth (height) is obtained. Finally numerical examples are treated.

quantities:

m = mass of the ball

r = radius of the ball

v = velocity of the ball

b = acceleration of the ball
 s = depth (height) of the ball
 φ_K = density of the ball
 φ = density of the liquid (gas)
 η = dynamic viscosity of the liquid (gas)
 c_w = drag coefficient
 t = time
 g = acceleration of free ball (due to gravity)
 λ = mean free path (gas)

$$a := 1 - \frac{\varphi}{\varphi_K}$$

$F(v)$ = resistance in a medium

a) liquids:

$$F(v) = \alpha_1 v^2 + \beta_1 v \quad (1)$$

α_1 and β_1 are functions from $r, \varphi_K, \varphi, \eta$ and c_w . With Budo [1] §92 p.525 (92.28), §94 p.535 (94.6), Kuchling [3] chapter 10.3.1. p.165 (M 10.20) and Timmermann [5] this formula is valid for $\frac{\varphi r v}{\eta} < 1$.

b) gas:

$$F(v) = \alpha_1 v^2 + \beta_1 v \quad (2)$$

α_1 and β_1 are functions from $r, \varphi_K, \varphi, \eta, c_w$ and λ . This is valid for $\frac{\lambda}{r} < 1$ see Budo [1] §92 p.525 between (92.28) and (92.29), see Kuchling [3] chapter 10.3.1. p.165 (M 10.20) and Timmermann [5].

equation of motion:

With Budo [1] §16 p.83 (16.3) and p.85 (16.21) it is valid:

$$m\dot{v} = mag - F(v) \quad v(0) = 0$$

an initial-value problem

This initial-value problem can be treated through the separation of variables.

$$F(v) = \alpha_1 v^2 + \beta_1 v \quad \alpha_1, \beta_1 > 0$$

$$m\dot{v} = mag - \alpha_1 v^2 - \beta_1 v$$

$$\dot{v} = A - Bv - Cv^2 \quad v(0) = 0$$

with

$$A := ag \quad B := \frac{\beta_1}{m} \quad C := \frac{\alpha_1}{m} \quad B, C > 0$$

If $a = 1 - \frac{\varphi}{\varphi_K} > 0$ then $A > 0$

(motion downward)

If $a < 0$ then $A < 0$

(motion upwards)

limits of velocity:

$$0 = \dot{v} = A - Bv - Cv^2$$

$$0 = Cv^2 + Bv - A$$

$$0 = v^2 + \frac{B}{C}v - \frac{A}{C}$$

$$v_{1,2} = \pm \sqrt{\frac{A}{C} + \left(\frac{B}{2C}\right)^2} - \frac{B}{2C}$$

$$= -\frac{B}{2C} \pm \sqrt{\frac{B^2}{4C^2} + \frac{4AC}{4C^2}}$$

$$= \frac{1}{2C} \cdot \left(-B \pm \sqrt{B^2 + 4AC}\right)$$

$$v_1 = \frac{1}{2C} \cdot \left(-B + \sqrt{B^2 + 4AC}\right) > 0$$

if $A > 0$

If $A < 0$, then $v_1 < 0$.

$$v_2 = \frac{1}{2C} \left(-B - \sqrt{B^2 + 4AC} \right) < 0$$

Factoring:

$$A - Bv - Cv^2 = -C(v - v_1)(v - v_2)$$

partial fraction decomposition:

$$\frac{1}{A - Bv - Cv^2} = \frac{\alpha}{v - v_1} + \frac{\beta}{v - v_2}$$

$$1 = -C\alpha(v - v_2) - C\beta(v - v_1)$$

$$v = v_1 \Rightarrow 1 = -C\alpha(v_1 - v_2) \quad \alpha = \frac{-1}{C(v_1 - v_2)}$$

$$v = v_2 \Rightarrow 1 = -C\beta(v_2 - v_1) \quad \beta = \frac{1}{C(v_1 - v_2)}$$

it follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{v} &= \frac{1}{A - Bv - Cv^2} = \frac{-1}{C(v_1 - v_2)(v - v_1)} + \frac{1}{C(v_1 - v_2)(v - v_2)} \\ &= \frac{-1}{C(v_1 - v_2)} \left(\frac{1}{v - v_1} - \frac{1}{v - v_2} \right) \end{aligned}$$

Integration: (separation of variables)

$$\begin{aligned} \int dt &= \int \frac{dv}{A - Bv - Cv^2} = \int \frac{-1}{C(v_1 - v_2)} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{v - v_1} - \frac{1}{v - v_2} \right) dv \\ &= \frac{-1}{C(v_1 - v_2)} \cdot (\ln |v - v_1| - \ln |v - v_2|) = t + d_1 \end{aligned}$$

d_1, d_2, d are integration constants.

$$\ln |v - v_2| - \ln |v - v_1| = C(v_1 - v_2)(t + d_1)$$

$$\ln \left| \frac{v - v_2}{v - v_1} \right| = C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t + d_2$$

$$\frac{v - v_2}{v - v_1} = de^{C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t} \tag{3}$$

$$v - v_2 = vde^{C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t} - v_1de^{C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t}$$

$$v \cdot \left(1 - de^{C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t} \right) = v_2 - v_1de^{C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t}$$

$$v = \frac{v_2 - v_1 d e^{C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t}}{1 - d e^{C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t}}$$

with $v(t=0) = 0$ and (3) we get $\frac{v_2}{v_1} = d$

$$v = \frac{v_2 - v_1 \frac{v_2}{v_1} e^{C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t}}{1 - \frac{v_2}{v_1} e^{C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t}}$$

$$v_2 < 0$$

$$v = \frac{v_2 \cdot (1 - e^{C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t})}{1 + \frac{|v_2|}{v_1} e^{C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t}}$$

$$v = \frac{v_2 (e^{-C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t} - 1)}{e^{-C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t} + \frac{|v_2|}{v_1}}$$

end velocity: $v_2 < 0$

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} v(t) = \frac{v_2(0 - 1)}{0 + \frac{|v_2|}{v_1}} = \frac{-v_2}{|v_2|} \cdot v_1 = v_1$$

$$v_1 = \frac{1}{2C} \left(-B + \sqrt{B^2 + 4AC} \right)$$

$$v = \frac{E(e^{Ft} - 1)}{e^{Ft} + G}$$

with

$$F := -C(v_1 - v_2) \quad E := v_2 \quad G := \frac{|v_2|}{v_1}$$

$$b(t) = \dot{v}(t) = E \cdot \frac{F e^{Ft} (e^{Ft} + G) - (e^{Ft} - 1) F e^{Ft}}{(e^{Ft} + G)^2}$$

$$= E \cdot \frac{F e^{Ft} (G + 1)}{(e^{Ft} + G)^2}$$

$$= v_2 \frac{-C(v_1 - v_2) e^{-C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t} \cdot \left(\frac{|v_2|}{v_1} + 1 \right)}{\left(e^{-C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t} + \frac{|v_2|}{v_1} \right)^2}$$

$$1) \quad \varphi_K > \varphi \quad \Rightarrow \quad a > 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad A > 0$$

$$v_2 < 0 \quad v_1 > 0 \quad C > 0$$

$$\Rightarrow \quad v_1 - v_2 > 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad -C(v_1 - v_2) < 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad v_2 \cdot (-C) \cdot (v_1 - v_2) > 0$$

$$\Rightarrow \quad \dot{v}(t) > 0$$

$\Rightarrow v(t)$ is a strictly increasing function.

$$2) \quad \varphi_K < \varphi \quad \Rightarrow \quad a < 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad A < 0$$

$$v_2 < 0 \quad v_1 < 0$$

$$a) \quad |v_2| > |v_1|$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{|v_2|}{v_1} + 1 < 0 \quad \text{and} \quad v_1 - v_2 > 0$$

$$\Rightarrow -Cv_2(v_1 - v_2) \cdot \left(\frac{|v_2|}{v_1} + 1 \right) < 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \dot{v}(t) < 0$$

$\Rightarrow v(t)$ is a strictly decreasing function.

$$b) \quad |v_2| < |v_1|$$

This case doesn't occur (see formulas v_1 and v_2).

Because $v(0) = 0$, it follows $v(t) > 0$ in case 1 ($a > 0$, motion downward) and in case 2 ($a < 0$, motion upwards) $v(t) < 0$.

Integration:

$$s(t) = \int v(t) dt = \int \frac{E(e^{Ft} - 1)}{e^{Ft} + G} dt$$

see Gröbner [2] volume 1 Nr. 311 p.107 2)

$$e^{Ft} = y \quad \text{thus} \quad t = \frac{1}{F} \ln y$$

$$\frac{dt}{dy} = \frac{1}{Fy} \quad y(t) = e^{Ft} \quad y(0) = 1$$

$$s(t) = \int_{y(0)}^{y(t)} \frac{E(y-1) dy}{(y+G)Fy} = \frac{E}{F} \cdot \int_{y(0)}^{y(t)} \frac{(y-1) dy}{y^2 + Gy}$$

partial fraction decomposition:

$$\frac{1}{y^2 + Gy} = \frac{\delta}{y} + \frac{\varepsilon}{y+G}$$

$$1 = \delta(y+G) + \varepsilon y = y(\delta + \varepsilon) + \delta G$$

$$1 = \delta G \quad \delta + \varepsilon = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow \delta = \frac{1}{G} \quad \varepsilon = -\frac{1}{G}$$

thus:

$$\frac{1}{y^2 + Gy} = \frac{1}{Gy} - \frac{1}{G(y+G)}$$

test:

$$\frac{1}{Gy} - \frac{1}{G(y+G)} = \frac{y+G-y}{Gy(y+G)} = \frac{G}{Gy(y+G)}$$

$$= \frac{1}{y(y+G)} = \frac{1}{y^2 + Gy}$$

thus:

$$\frac{F}{E} \cdot s(t) = \int_{y(0)}^{y(t)} \left(\frac{y-1}{Gy} - \frac{y-1}{G(y+G)} \right) dy$$

see Gröbner [2] Nr. 12 p.7 4c):

$$= \left[\frac{y}{G} - \frac{\ln|y|}{G} - \frac{y-1}{G} - \frac{-1 \cdot G^2 + (-1) \cdot G}{G^2} \cdot \ln|G(y+G)| \right]_{y(0)}^{y(t)}$$

$$= \left[\frac{y - \ln|y|}{G} - \frac{y-1}{G} + \frac{G+1}{G} \cdot \ln|G(y+G)| \right]_{y(0)}^{y(t)}$$

test using differentiation:

$$\frac{d}{dy} \frac{E}{F} \cdot \left(\frac{y}{G} - \frac{\ln|y|}{G} - \frac{y-1}{G} + \frac{G+1}{G} \ln|G(y+G)| \right)$$

$$= \frac{E}{F} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{G} - \frac{1}{Gy} - \frac{1}{G} + \frac{G+1}{G} \cdot \frac{G}{G(y+G)} \right)$$

$$= \frac{E}{F} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{G} - \frac{1}{Gy} - \frac{1}{G} + \frac{G+1}{G(y+G)} \right)$$

$$= \frac{E}{F} \cdot \left(\frac{y-1}{Gy} + \frac{-y-G+G+1}{G(y+G)} \right)$$

$$= \frac{E}{F} \cdot \left(\frac{y-1}{Gy} + \frac{1-y}{G(y+G)} \right) = \frac{E}{F} \cdot \left(\frac{y-1}{Gy} - \frac{y-1}{G(y+G)} \right)$$

The antiderivative is confirmed.

$$y(t) = e^{Ft} \quad y(0) = 1$$

thus:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{F}{E} \cdot s(t) &= \frac{e^{Ft} - Ft}{G} - \frac{e^{Ft} - 1}{G} + \frac{G+1}{G} \cdot \ln |G(e^{Ft} + G)| \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{G} - \frac{G+1}{G} \cdot \ln |G(1+G)| \\ &= \frac{e^{Ft} - Ft}{G} - \frac{e^{Ft} - 1}{G} - \frac{1}{G} + \frac{G+1}{G} \ln \left| \frac{e^{Ft} + G}{1+G} \right| \end{aligned}$$

we conclude:

$$s(t) = \frac{E}{F} \left(\frac{e^{Ft} - Ft}{G} - \frac{e^{Ft} - 1}{G} - \frac{1}{G} + \frac{G+1}{G} \cdot \ln \left| \frac{e^{Ft} + G}{1+G} \right| \right)$$

$$s(t) = \frac{E}{GF} \left(e^{Ft} - Ft - e^{Ft} + 1 - 1 + (G+1) \cdot \ln \left| \frac{e^{Ft} + G}{1+G} \right| \right)$$

$$s(t) = \frac{E}{FG} \left((G+1) \cdot \ln \left| \frac{e^{Ft} + G}{1+G} \right| - Ft \right)$$

$$F = -C(v_1 - v_2) \quad G = \frac{|v_2|}{v_1} \quad E = v_2$$

$$s(t) = \frac{v_2 \cdot v_1}{-C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot |v_2|} \cdot \left(\left(\frac{|v_2|}{v_1} + 1 \right) \cdot \ln \left| \frac{e^{-C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t} + \frac{|v_2|}{v_1}}{1 + \frac{|v_2|}{v_1}} \right| + C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t \right)$$

$v_2 < 0$

$$= \frac{v_1}{C(v_1 - v_2)} \cdot \left(\left(\frac{|v_2|}{v_1} + 1 \right) \cdot \ln \left| \frac{e^{-C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t} + \frac{|v_2|}{v_1}}{1 + \frac{|v_2|}{v_1}} \right| + C(v_1 - v_2) \cdot t \right)$$

thus $s(t=0) = 0$

s must not be too large, because of the pressure(gas) and the density (liquid). The free fall in the air with pressure change is treated in Shea [4].

Now we occupy with two numerical examples. First we treat the free fall in air (density= $0.0012928 \frac{kg}{m^3}$ at zero degree Celsius and 101.3 Kilopascal). The ball's radius is 0.05 m, the mass=4kg. thus a density of 7.6394 gram per cubic centimetre. The drag coefficient is $c_m=0.4$. The viscosity η has got the value 0.0000172 [pascal seconds]. In the following table there are time, acceleration, velocity and depth:

$t[s]$	acceleration $[\frac{m}{s^2}]$	velocity $[\frac{m}{s}]$	depth[m]
0	9.80577	0	0
1	9.80572	9.80576	4.90288
2	9.80558	19.61141	19.61148
3	9.80533	29.41688	44.12565
4	9.80499	39.22205	78.44514
5	9.80455	49.02683	122.56961
6	9.80402	58.83112	176.49863
7	9.80338	68.63483	240.23166
8	9.80265	78.43785	313.76806
9	9.80182	88.24009	397.10710
10	9.80089	98.04146	490.24795

We turn to a second example: The free fall of a ball in water. Here the density is $0.9982 \frac{kg}{dm^3}$ at 20 degree Celsius and the viscosity $\eta = 0.001002$ pascal seconds. The other quantities remain unchanged. The resistance is more remarkable. This is shown in the following table:

$t[s]$	acceleration $[\frac{m}{s^2}]$	velocity $[\frac{m}{s}]$	depth [m]
0	6.54589	0	0
1	6.34437	6.47815	3.25594
2	5.78724	12.56935	12.82629
3	4.99458	17.97388	28.16417
4	4.10891	22.52780	48.48899
5	3.24942	26.20096	72.92509
6	2.49056	29.06069	100.61920
7	1.66361	31.22639	130.81499
8	1.36960	32.83239	162.88552
9	0.99329	34.00488	196.33549
10	0.71348	34.85114	230.78679

References

- [1] A.Budo "Theoretische Mechanik" 10.edition 1980 Deutscher Verlag der Wissenschaften
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- [5] P.Timmermann, J. van der Weele "On the rise and fall of a ball with linear or quadratic drag" Am.J.Phys. 67 (6), June 1999 p.538-546